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Introduction

Mohandas karamchand Gandhi is popularly known as ‘Gandhi ji’ out of reverence. ‘Bapu’ out of affection, ‘Mahatma’ on account of saintly nature and ‘father of the nation’, for his role in the freedom of Indian from British rule.

Gandhi ji was born on October 2, 1869 at porbandar in Gujrat. His father was a dewan of small state. At school, he was slow, hesitate and shy. He was married to Kasturba at the age of thirteen. His mother was very pious and he was greatly influenced by her.

When 18 years old, he was sent to London to study law where he remained for three years. After returning from England, he started his law practice at Bombay. However, he was not very successful.

In April, 1839 he went to South Africa in connection with civil law case of a firm. In 1893 itself, he was thrown out of a first class compartment in Durbin (South Africa) for he was a coloured man. He stayed there for about 20 years. This was a turning point in his life. Gandhi ji found that Indians in South Africa were treated very cruelly and in fact like animals. They had no political rights. Gandhi ji took up cases which were not entirely not political bit touched intimately the life of the people. He completely devoted himself to the service of the people. He put into practice ‘satyagraha’ and ‘Ahinsa’.

Gandhi ji educational experiments

Gandhi ji philosophy of life including philosophy of education took shape in South Africa. In South Africa he formulating a new system of education. The children had to devote 8 hours a day for vocational training and 2 hours to book reading. ‘Learning by doing’ and learning by cooperation’ became chief methods of education.

Gandhi ji publication on education

- My experiment with truth
- Basic education
- Towards need education

- True education
- To the students
- Task before Indian students
- India of my dreams
- Medium of instruction
- Task for India

Factors influenced Gandhi ji philosophy of education

- Gandhi ji mother taught him the lesson of simplicity and piety
- Rayachand Bhai Patel who taught him the first lesson in non- violence ,
- Ruskin, through his book ‘unto the last’ drew his attention to the principal of dignity of labour,
- Leo Tolstoy’s ‘the kingdom of the god is within you ‘greatly influenced his spiritual outlook.
- At Tolstoy farm he taught vocations such as cooking, digging, and message work. Children learn by doing.
- Textbook were not used. The medium of instruction was mother tongue. English was taught.
- Creed of non-violence was put into practice and spirit.

Gandhi ji views on different aspect of education

- Gandhi ji summed up his ideas on education in these words “by education I mean all – round drawing out of the best and man body, mind and spirit. All round implies the harmonious of the individual. Man is neither mere the gross animal body, nor intellectual and nor the heart and soul alone. A proper and harmonious combination of all these is required for making the whole man.
- The ultimate objective of education is not only a balanced and harmonious individual but also a balanced harmonious society- a just social order in which there is no unnatural dividing the heavens and have – nots and everybody is assured of a living wage and right to freedom.
- Students should learn and side by side earn by doing some work in the school
- Craft should become the source and centre of learning
- Education should be imparted in such a way through craft and their products/manufactured articles by the students should meet some expenditure in running the school
- Mother tongue should be the medium of instruction.
- Gandhi ji advocated same facilities for women’s for men and special facilities where necessary.
- According to him a teacher has to be both father and mother to his pupils.

Sum up

Scheme of education is its emphasis is on relating school education to the needs of the society. He wanted to achieve this objective through a system of 'learning while earning' He gave an important place to the learning craft. His emphasis on education through the mother tongue is the accepted principle by all thinkers. Gandhi ji stress on inculcating dignity of labour is the Ned of the hour. There is the dire need to develop elements of spirituality in our life which is do dominated by materialism.

“IF WE WANT TO REACH REAL PEACE IN THIS WORLD, WE SHOULD START EDUCATING CHILDREN”

- M.K.Gandhi